

Soak aways and local storm water drainage

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As a result of climate changes we are experiencing more and more heavy rainfalls as we have seen in Copenhagen the last couple of years. These rainfalls cause great damage on low-lying areas. The sewerage systems in Denmark are not build to handle extreme amounts of rain and therefore we have to come up with an alternative solution. One solution is to use local storm water drainage such as soak aways. This project aims to model how three specifically chosen soak aways handle and hold back rainwater. The project is made in cooperation with Orbicon, Avedøre Spildevandscenter and Rudersdal Kommune.